

LEARNING IN A DIGITAL WORLD - AN INNOVATIVE AREA OF PISA 2025

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Abstract.

This article analyzes the main directions, updates, and innovative approaches of the PISA 2025 international student assessment program. In the PISA 2025 cycle, the concept of scientific literacy was expanded to include decision-making competencies related to sustainable development and technological processes. The content of the concept "Acting in the Anthropocene" and the innovative direction "Learning in the Digital World" is also analyzed.

Keywords. PISA 2025, innovative approaches, sustainable development, anthropocene, concept, learning in the digital world.

The ninth cycle of the PISA study will take place in 2025, with 89 countries participating. PISA is an international student assessment program designed to measure 15-year-olds' ability to use their knowledge and skills in reading, mathematics, and science to solve real-life problems.

In addition to the three core areas, PISA assesses one innovative area, which changes each cycle. Furthermore, each cycle alternates between the three areas of focus. In 2025, the focus will be on scientific literacy, meaning that the majority of questions and assignments will be devoted to assessing this area.

So, what's new in the PISA 2025 cycle: The science literacy assessment framework has been updated. The assessment framework identifies the competencies developed through science education, the types of knowledge students

need to develop these competencies, and the types of contexts in which students encounter science-related problems and questions in real life.

In 2025, the PISA framework will expand the concept of "scientific literacy" to include broader science education outcomes. According to the definition, scientific literacy involves the ability to reason cogently about science, sustainable development, and technology to justify action. This requires skills such as:

- 1) the ability to explain natural and technological phenomena scientifically;
- 2) the ability to design and evaluate scientific research projects and interpret scientific data and evidence critically;
- 3) the ability to explore global, local, or personal issues, evaluate scientific information, and use it to make decisions and take informed actions.

Furthermore, the concept of "Acting in the Anthropocene" has been added to the assessment framework, defining a range of competencies aimed at addressing environmental issues and sustainability in an era of intense human activity and impact on nature. The concept of factors influencing student competencies has also been amended, shifting the focus from attitudes toward natural science to measuring a broader concept—"self-determination in relation to natural science."

In June of this year, the natural science framework and sample questions were published in 25 languages, including Kazakh and Russian.

The PISA program assesses reading, mathematical, and scientific literacy. Since 2012, in addition to the three areas listed above, a fourth (innovative) area has been assessed, which changes each cycle. Thus, in 2012, the innovative research area was creative problem solving, in 2015, collaborative problem solving, in 2018, global competencies, and in 2022, creative thinking. In 2025, the innovative area will be learning in the digital world.

Including assessment of the innovative area in the research assessment framework allows for a broader understanding of functional literacy. Furthermore, it enables a more comprehensive assessment of the level of "readiness for real life" among 15-year-old students.

The purpose of assessing learning in the digital world is:

- 1) to determine the extent to which students are able to be successful and independent in the digital world;
- 2) to provide relevant and comparable data on the use of digital technologies in education and student learning outcomes.

This area assesses test takers' readiness for independent learning in the digital world. The tasks are designed to assess students' ability to learn new concepts and use tools (e.g., programs, simulations, models) to solve problems in the digital world. Students complete two 30-minute blocks of tasks (or modules), each consisting of four phases: a pre-test to determine their level, interactive learning, a practical part, and problem solving.

The assessment tracks students' actions to measure their progress toward achieving their goals throughout the task and how well they utilize learning resources (examples, hints, and feedback).

Education technologies can transform how students learn because they offer them new opportunities to explore complex phenomena and to create digital representations of their ideas they can tinker with and share with others. Yet, not enough attention has been devoted to teaching the foundational skills and attitudes that students need to develop in order to be active and autonomous users of technology for confronting open-ended, real world problems.

The PISA 2025 Learning in the Digital World assessment focuses on two competencies that are essential to learning with technologies: self-regulated

learning, which refers to the monitoring and control of one's metacognitive, cognitive, behavioural, motivational and affective processes while learning; and computational and scientific inquiry practices, which refer to the capacity to use digital tools to explore systems, represent ideas and solve problems with computational logic.

As technology advances, it is increasingly important that young people are prepared to take part in a workforce in which computers play an ever-increasing role and to make decisions about how to use technology for acquiring new knowledge and skills. While not everyone will become software engineers, jobs of the future will increasingly require people to interact with computational models and simulated realities, and to solve problems using digital tools. Given the rapid rate of technological change, students today must develop a set of broad skills and perspectives that support lifelong learning in novel and unfamiliar digital environments.

The PISA 2025 Learning in the Digital World assessment presents several major innovations for PISA. Each test unit is designed as a modern, digital learning environment where students can find a range of resources to fill their knowledge gaps, such as tutorials or worked examples, and where they get intelligent feedback on their progress. In this open-ended environment with low floors and high ceilings, students have to make choices on how much time they dedicate to different sub-tasks, develop strategies on how to tackle complex problems, and monitor and evaluate their progress. Students' performance is evaluated not just on their capacity to respond correctly to questions, but also on the extent to which they can build a tangible representation of their emerging understanding, which is represented as a program or a computational model. For the first time, PISA will provide international comparisons of students self-regulated learning processes, including measures of

motivation and emotion regulation. This evidence is built by combining response and process data through innovative analytical models. The results of the PISA 2025 Learning in the Digital World assessment are expected to be available in 2027

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